

Implementing Evidence Based Navigation Systems in Medical Buildings

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Abstract. The stress and urgency of hospital visits call for the need for universal, easily understandable navigation systems. In this work-in-progress paper we introduce a complex methodology focused on inclusive design, iterative testing and utilization of modern technologies providing objective data, all in the highly specific context of medical buildings (research through design). We aim to create efficient and universal manual for the design of navigation systems and complementary adjustable virtual testing environment.

Keywords. Wayfinding, Eye Tracking, Virtual Reality, Inclusive Design

1. Introduction

Health facilities are one of the most complex structures that are also highly dynamic –new buildings are constructed; departments are relatively often moved and the altogether purpose of particular building may change in years and not correspond to the intended architectural design anymore. Many users with different agendas meet here daily - from patients, visitors and local employees to external emergency doctors and food delivery workers and they all rely on the same navigational system which isn't always effective. Furthermore, during hospital visits, people are often very stressed which can negatively affect spatial navigation (Lerner et al. 2015, Bae et al. 2020, Tian et al. 2020). Together with higher probability of occurrence of people with (temporal) cognitive disadvantage, the need for extremely effective and easily comprehensive navigation system arises. The best approach to navigation systems in hospitals is researched worldwide (Ahmed et al. 2022, Lu & Bozovic-Stamenovic 2009) and is far from concluded.

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The goal of this project is to map users' needs regarding the navigation systems in health facilities with focus on users with various special needs who are very often completely overlooked during the design; illustrate the importance of iterative design testing; and present appropriate principles for new designs including concrete examples of good approaches based on the research we conducted in three different hospitals. All of this will come together in a manual that should help other medical facilities create more efficient signatures as the problems with navigation they face are highly overlapping.

2. Methodology

We closely cooperate with one hospital who is our grant partner, but we also collect data in other hospitals as well. This way we can generalise the findings and look for more universal requirements for the navigation systems.

There are four stages of testing planned (*Fig. 1*). The first one was evaluating the current state of the navigation system. Apart from semi-structured interviews with the staff and expert evaluations of the hospital accessibility, we arranged extensive user testing with first time visitors-participants. For this user testing we designed multiple destination customer journeys both in- and outdoors. The participants wore eye tracking glasses and were instructed to narrate their behaviour. For the analysis we worked with visual attention, time and distance of the routes and participants' statements.

Based on these findings, three designer studios designed new navigation systems. These designs were recently evaluated in the second testing. This time no users' performance was tested but the general appeal and comprehension of the designs, including their fit into the spatial context of the hospital's surroundings, was discussed in focus groups. Further, an expert committee evaluated the designs as well.

Based on these evaluations, two best designs were selected and tasked with signature redesign – especially focusing on the accessibility layer. These designs will be then tested in the virtual hospital in the summer. In this phase, the users' performance will be evaluated the same way it was in the preliminary testing – each participant will have to find multiple targets (corresponding to the targets in the first preliminary testing). In this testing we will be able to directly compare efficiency of the original and new designs.

Finally, the best design might be slightly redesigned. In the final phase the system will be installed in the real-world hospital and validated again with eye tracking testing.

Figure 1. The testing and redesign plan.

2.1. Inclusive Design

Even though it could be expected that people with special needs might be visiting hospital complexes more frequently, they are rarely included in wayfinding research (Gupta et al. 2020). We aim to include them and thoroughly map the needs of specific groups (senior citizens, neurodivergent people¹, people with hearing and physical disabilities) and describe ways how to accommodate these needs.

2.2. Eye Tracking

We use SMI Glasses 2 for eye tracking with 60 Hz sampling frequency. We mainly focus on navigation signs and the way they are read (in the first testing we could see that some crucial parts of the signs were completely avoided by users' which led to disorientation). Apart from the eye movements the glasses also record the sound and participants surroundings. We used this feature to track the position of the participants and to record their thought regarding the orientation in real time (*think aloud protocol*).

2.3. Immersive Virtual Reality Testing

We decided to test the designs in virtual environment for financial and logistic reasons. A copy of the most complex building and the outdoors will be created (exhibition of the indoor environment is in *Figure 2*) where participants will be able to freely move through the environment. We will collect the data with the HMD Varjo - XR-4 which has integrated 200Hz eye tracking. The final environment will be adjustable for possible future use on different hospitals, as the exact replica of the environment isn't needed for sign evaluation – only certain aspects of the environment must be corre-

¹ In our case people with ADHD, ASD and dyslexia

sponding to the original (colouring, lighting, corridors width, staircases, visual smog, etc.).

Figure 2. Exhibition of the virtual environment. Lighting, more specifically lightmapping settings, distribution and type of light sources in the environment, and reflection settings of glossy objects, will be subject to final adjustments.

3. Preliminary results – case presentation

Shortly the results of the most difficult target in the indoor will be introduced. In this part of the research, participants were instructed to find the ENT exam room starting on the fourth floor. In *Figure 3* you can see the shortest way using both the staircase and the elevator and the cumulative route of all the participants and in *Figure 4* more detailed comparison of two particular participants. We can see that participants weren't able to locate the target floor and once they did, they weren't able to locate the target door on it. From the eye tracking data we know that the visual attention was scattered evenly between real navigation signs and visual smog which on this floor is higher than anywhere else.

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